

Agisoft Metashape

Processing Report
08 September 2025

Survey Data

Fig. 1. Camera locations and image overlap.

Number of images:	242	Camera stations:	241
Flying altitude:	29.5 cm	Tie points:	173,726
Ground resolution:	0.0334 mm/pix	Projections:	600,112
Coverage area:	436 cm ²	Reprojection error:	0.297 pix

Camera Model	Resolution	Focal Length	Pixel Size	Precalibrated
NIKON D5500 (35mm)	6000 x 4000	35 mm	4.04 x 4.04 μm	No

Table 1. Cameras.

Camera Calibration

Fig. 2. Image residuals for NIKON D5500 (35mm).

NIKON D5500 (35mm)

242 images

Type	Resolution	Focal Length	Pixel Size
Frame	6000 x 4000	35 mm	4.04 x 4.04 μm

F: 8827.13

Cx: 0.93698

Cy: -12.9019

K1: -0.0466048

K2: 2.23138

K3: -16.6503

K4: 48.8938

B1: -2.85543

B2: 0.203504

P1: -0.000320987

P2: -0.00104146

P3: 0

P4: 0

Scale Bars

Label	Distance (m)	Error (m)
point 1_point 2	0.1	1.81799e-15
Total		1.81799e-15

Table 2. Control scale bars.

Digital Elevation Model

Fig. 3. Reconstructed digital elevation model.

Resolution: unknown
Point density: unknown

Processing Parameters

General

Cameras	242
Aligned cameras	241
Markers	23
Scale bars	1
Coordinate system	Local Coordinates (m)
Rotation angles	Yaw, Pitch, Roll

Tie Points

Points	173,726 of 402,321
RMS reprojection error	0.140275 (0.296595 pix)
Max reprojection error	0.465477 (2.47156 pix)
Mean key point size	2.00273 pix
Point colors	3 bands, uint8
Key points	No
Average tie point multiplicity	3.53983

Alignment parameters

Accuracy	Highest
Generic preselection	Yes
Reference preselection	No
Key point limit	40,000
Key point limit per Mpx	1,000
Tie point limit	6,000
Filter points by mask	Yes
Mask tie points	No
Exclude stationary tie points	Yes
Guided image matching	No
Adaptive camera model fitting	Yes
Matching time	3 minutes 30 seconds
Matching memory usage	623.13 MB
Alignment time	1 minutes 30 seconds
Alignment memory usage	592.55 MB

Optimization parameters

Parameters	f, b1, b2, cx, cy, k1-k4, p1, p2
Adaptive camera model fitting	No
Optimization time	7 seconds
Date created	2025:07:07 12:07:28
Software version	2.2.1.20592
File size	26.89 MB

Depth Maps

Count	238
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Depth maps generation parameters

Quality	Ultra High
Filtering mode	Mild
Max neighbors	16
Processing time	21 minutes 21 seconds
Memory usage	11.47 GB
Date created	2025:07:07 12:55:02
Software version	2.2.1.20592
File size	956.17 MB

Point Cloud

Points	41,788,246
Point attributes	
Position	8.54 μ m
Color	3 bands, uint8
Normal	
Confidence	
Point classes	
Created (never classified)	41,788,246
Depth maps generation parameters	
Quality	Ultra High
Filtering mode	Mild
Max neighbors	16
Processing time	21 minutes 21 seconds
Memory usage	11.47 GB
Point cloud generation parameters	
Processing time	25 minutes 33 seconds
Memory usage	45.74 GB
Date created	2025:07:07 13:20:45
Software version	2.2.1.20592
File size	1.26 GB
Model	
Faces	15,556,913
Vertices	7,788,759
Vertex colors	3 bands, uint8
Texture	14,192 x 14,192, 4 bands, uint8
Depth maps generation parameters	
Quality	Ultra High
Filtering mode	Mild
Max neighbors	16
Processing time	21 minutes 21 seconds
Memory usage	11.47 GB
Point cloud generation parameters	
Processing time	25 minutes 33 seconds
Memory usage	45.74 GB
Reconstruction parameters	
Surface type	Arbitrary
Source data	Point cloud
Interpolation	Enabled
Strict volumetric masks	No
Processing time	9 minutes 58 seconds
Memory usage	8.71 GB
Texturing parameters	
Mapping mode	Generic
Blending mode	Mosaic
Texture size	14,192
Enable hole filling	Yes
Enable ghosting filter	Yes
UV mapping time	1 minutes 35 seconds
UV mapping memory usage	2.48 GB
Blending time	1 minutes 56 seconds
Blending memory usage	9.73 GB
Blending GPU memory usage	5.78 GB
Date created	2025:07:09 07:57:14
Software version	2.2.1.20592
File size	890.04 MB
System	

Software name	Agisoft Metashape Professional
Software version	2.0.1 build 16069
OS	Windows 64 bit
RAM	15.78 GB
CPU	Intel(R) Core(TM) i5-10500H CPU @ 2.50GHz
GPU(s)	Intel(R) UHD Graphics NVIDIA GeForce RTX 3050 Ti Laptop GPU